

PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE THROUGH INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES TO STUDENTS OF A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION WHO DO NOT SPECIALIZE ON LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *We are currently working to improve the younger generation's exposure to foreign languages, the system for training foreign language specialists, and the training of qualified specialists who meet international educational standards by becoming fluent in foreign languages. A contemporary necessity is to recognize the chances for learning and strengthening the teacher's language abilities, the students' creativity, their passion for the topic, and the formation of relationships with the students. The resolution calls for the improvement of the level and caliber of the preparation of highly qualified foreign language teachers for secondary schools, professional colleges, academic lyceums, and higher educational institutions, and calls for measures to be implemented in accordance with international standards. Each language learned has its own rules, principles, and principles at the same time. The student must be aware of the most subtle nuances of the language in order to become a highly competent individual who satisfies worldwide standards.*

Keywords: *pedagogical technology, artificial intelligence, open databases, the ethics of using data.*

INTRODUCTION

In our republic, new guidelines and standards for teaching foreign languages and evaluating the knowledge and abilities of foreign language instructors have been devised in accordance with the CEFR's recommendations. It claims that textbooks were written with general education and vocational college students in mind. These specifications led to the installation of stands and modern information and communication methods in classrooms. Learning a foreign language is becoming more and more popular. Reading, speaking, hearing, and speaking are the four components of foreign language science, and distinct ideas and abilities are provided for each of them. Modern information technologies are effectively used in the educational process through educational technology. By incorporating cutting-edge, new technology into the educational process, it also offers for improving the quality and effectiveness of instruction. Utilizing such information and communication technology in particular has a number of benefits for learning a foreign language.

The textbooks, training courses, and guides that are currently being developed to radically adapt our nation's educational system to foreign languages serve as the concrete evidence of these objectives. Thus, the only student who can study foreign languages with love is one who is well-versed in both his own tongue and culture. Similar careful planning is needed to learn foreign languages. Here, the question of why learning a second language is necessary emerges.

The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan developed a number of decisions and decrees aimed at learning foreign languages, which are considered to be the most urgent in order

to ensure that Uzbekistan quickly integrates into the global community. His goal was to lay a strong foundation for our nation's future prospects. For instance, if we take a look at Decision No. 1875 from December 10, 2012, "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Learning Foreign Languages," its main focus is on educating young people in foreign languages across the whole country of Uzbekistan. This choice is being made to guarantee that the next generation can communicate clearly in another language.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

We will get the chance to interact with young people from across the world, share ideas with them, thoroughly examine the process, and assess our own strengths and weaknesses in comparison to theirs through learning other languages. The phrase "He who knows a language knows" and the desire to acquire different languages are legacies of our ancient predecessors, such as Farabi, who was fluent in many languages, and Kashgari, who had a broad perspective on the comparative study of numerous languages.

Additionally, Abdulla Avloni addressed in depth the necessity of learning a language in order to stay up with the rest of the world in his 1913 essay "Not two languages are necessary" that appeared in the "Oyna" journal. Because they were able to communicate their scientific discoveries and unparalleled works to other countries in their own languages, our great-grandfathers are known and respected throughout the whole world. Honor is given to the Central Asian enlightenment, science, and culture. As we have often stated, language proficiency is the key to all of this.

It is evident why learning other languages is so important for today's youth: it allows them to connect with people in other countries directly, express their own opinions clearly and fluently in front of others, and establish Uzbekistan as a unique member of the international community. It is critical to acquire global language skills in order to maintain and enhance one's position.

Awareness and analysis of news in the cultural-educational, socioeconomic, and sporting arenas, as well as in the fields of medical and sports, are required to maintain and enhance Uzbekistan's unique position in the international community. The world's population must be shown the past's rich culture as well as the remarkable achievements of today's young. In this instance, the language undoubtedly serves as a link.

However, it should also be highlighted that ideas like state language, national language, and mother tongue should always be at the forefront for all of us, in addition to listing the benefits of language study that only serve good. needed. Since every autonomous nation has its own official tongue, Uzbek is a representation of Uzbekistan's independence. The acquisition of a second language should not imply that one's usage of the first language is constrained. Language is a reflection of the country and a symbol of the state. Every country has a moral obligation to develop it for the benefit of the following generation by adding to it, refining it, broadening the range of its applications, etc. The foundation for preserving the balance of languages in today's society is the flawless study of foreign languages and the use of each in its proper context to aid in the growth of the national language.

English language classes are offered in the higher education system of our republic in order to develop the ability to read original literature and engage in oral communication in a foreign language. This is done in the process of training future employees and gathering information required for scientific purposes. wishing A professional in his area should be able to read and comprehend original English-language works that are relevant to his line of work as well as apply

them to it. He should also be able to openly discuss the subject with the interlocutor in a foreign language.

Teaching English through interactive methods in higher education institutions that do not specialize in the language has a positive impact on students' ability to think critically, receive and give information in English, learn new vocabulary, and conduct scientific research in their field. It broadens the perspectives of pupils and enables you to keep up with developments. Working on material that is pertinent, or on subjects related to their career, is fascinating and helpful for students. For this, the learner must first be familiar with the definition, use, and pronunciation of any new words or terminology found in the book. For this, a variety of interactive techniques are useful. The "chain" (chain drill) approach is one illustration. The first student repeats the word without the translation and adds another word they have acquired after listening to the audio of a new phrase or term, which they have learnt and pronounced well. As a result, the game goes on until the final student says their phrase since the student who is repeating the words can assist him by stating this word only in Uzbek or Russian, and if he is unable to pronounce it, he will quit the game. The learner may learn new words more quickly and with interest thanks to this game. The second method: the group is divided into 2 or 3 small groups and they stand in a row and reinforce the words through the game "broken telephone".

This involves the first student creating a statement with the use of brand-new words and phrases, then telling it to the student behind him. That student then teaches the next student, and so on. Once the final student is reached, the game ends. The fundamental objective of the game is to cooperate as a team, try to thoroughly comprehend each student's idea, and give each student's presentation with accountability. They take in a lot of knowledge while understanding and communicating. The first group to deliver their opinion without error is declared the winner. Now it becomes much easier to work with groups that have mastered words. Students listen to the text in audio and follow the written form. When the audio is played the second time, the teacher distributes the new words from the same text in the same state. The student should fill it in at the same time without looking at anything. The result of this practical work is checked with all group students and errors are worked on. Now the text is divided into 2 or 3 parts and distributed to groups. Depending on the capacity of the group, time is set and they are given a task in the style of the game "Speaker with Translator", in which each of the students works as a translator and a speaker, that is, he translates the speaker's speech not dot by dot, but tone by tone, and the next sentence is eloquent. This is how the unit works. The rest of the groups observe their mistakes and shortcomings and write "feedback" on their work and talk in English about what they have understood with the help of their speech and translation. The rest of the groups work the same way. The grade is set by the students themselves. In this practical exercise, each student works for the quality output of their group work.

These techniques are particularly helpful in non-philological educational institutions for quick and simple word and term learning, independent thought expression, explaining to peers, and active participation in elective classes. They also serve to improve the teaching abilities of students of the same level. At the conclusion of the class, the teacher may provide a specific statement to each student that serves as incentive. The task of gathering more information about the provided text or processed texts and creating various presentations is delegated to groups. This allows them the chance to work without the aid of dictionaries and will assist them in finding additional knowledge on the subject, exchanging views and connecting their thoughts based on the

presentations that have been made. It is clear that the student engages in the class out of a desire to learn and broaden his knowledge, not out of boredom or a romantic interest in the work.

RESULTS

To use additional resources in teaching foreign languages to students, to increase the interest and attitude of students to a foreign language through auxiliary educational tools, to conduct each lesson in interactive, i.e., active-student methods, to give them additional lessons after the lessons and this process requires extensive use of traditional methods. In the course of classes organized using innovative technologies, students' interest in foreign languages increases, and their skills and abilities of independent creative work are improved. According to the etymology of the term "innovative technology" in the scientific literature, it means "innovation" (in English innovation - introduced innovation, invention, "newness" introduced in science and technology), and "technology" as a linguistic and didactic concept means "less time, energy". and means a set of rational methods of scientific organization of efforts that ensure the achievement of the educational goal. Cinquain, Brainstorming, Case, Zigzag, Cluster, Project, Method as specific methods of innovative technology in traditional pedagogy, the use of such types as Mind Mapping brought great results.

We shall discuss emerging new pedagogies in the sections that follow.

1) Education and artificial intelligence. Computer systems are referred described as having "artificial intelligence" (AI). Systems for teaching with artificial intelligence are fast becoming available in schools, colleges, and universities. Although the majority of people associate artificial intelligence with robot professors, it does have certain advantages. Intelligent learning systems, dialog-based learning systems, inquiry-based learning environments, automatic writing evaluations, and conversational agents are just a few examples of applications made specifically for students. Although less established, programs for teachers are programs that aid in instructors' knowledge advancement. It is important to note that abilities like critical thinking, creativity, communication, and teamwork possessed by both students and teachers should be taken into consideration. It would be fantastic if academics, learning specialists, and other interested parties worked together to create AI applications and instructional strategies.

2) Learning through open data. More than 250 national, local and municipal governments and organizations worldwide are sharing, creating and using data in their work. These organizations seek to see the data used by the public, and many mature services provide resources for open data exploration. Later initiatives led them to innovative education. So, the question is - what does open data offer as material? What is its importance in learning and teaching? The main factor is authenticity. Shared data emerges from real-world processes within large organizations. Information that is often used in professional work has a real impact on our lives and the world around us. The second factor is the importance of data in enhancing students' capacity. This can be a very powerful psychological effect. Students can compare events happening in their cities, villages, and even in their classrooms with events happening near and far. Perhaps in the process, they can also identify problems and draw local or community-wide attention to this problem.

In one instance, high school students in Italy received rewards for undertaking construction tasks while studying public funding. It demonstrates how social movements for improved incentives for data literacy, transparency, and evidence-based activities have arisen. Open data has connected readers.

3) Dealing with the ethics of information use. The growing use of digital technologies in education comes with ever-increasing ethical questions. There are many ethical issues here, such as who owns the data, how to interpret the data, and how to protect the privacy of students and faculty. There have also been cases of criticism of people they are not aware of. Maybe it's just a matter of time. In order to prevent such problems, educational institutions should develop a policy related to data ethics, obtain consent from students for the use of data, analyze any data from their interactions, and get acquainted with their opinions about the educational management system. , the creation of an effective teaching system, as well as issues of student and staff support must also be taken into account. There are currently no formal training sessions. For this, teachers should create opportunities for students. In today's digital world, mutual information exchange between institutes and universities increases their efficiency.

DISCUSSION

Modern technology plays an unparalleled role in both teaching and learning languages. Every component of learning a foreign language—reading, reading, hearing, and speaking—benefits from the use of technology. For instance, this procedure obviously requires a computer, player, and CDs in order to listen and comprehend. One of the most crucial aspects of language learning is listening comprehension. The reader must also focus on the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammar standards, and use of terminology and its meanings. Students' knowledge of and proficiency with information and communication technologies is a key component in the usage of contemporary technologies in the educational process. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. In this process, among other things:

- when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons;
- it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs;
- use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method;
- CD players can be used.

The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. Today, teaching through interactive games is becoming a tradition in educational institutions. It is known that the lesson is conducted on the basis of various games, which ensures that students demonstrate their capabilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. Such life-like role-playing games create a language environment in the course of the lesson, and give students the opportunity to express their thoughts freely. In the process of participating in role-playing games, students learn to think, learn to express their emotional states freely in a foreign language. In the process of preparing for role-playing games, they correct each other's lexical, grammatical and pronunciation mistakes. correcting this mistake also helps to learn the language and teaches students to pronounce correctly. Using role-playing games during the lesson ensures that all students are actively participating in the lesson at the same time. In addition, role-playing games increase students' interest in learning a foreign language and create a lively, fun atmosphere for the lesson process. This serves to increase the effectiveness of foreign language lessons.

The activity that engages and accelerates the student forms the cornerstone of the usage of gaming technology. The psychological mechanics of playful action, according to psychologists, are based on a person's basic desires to express himself, find a secure position in life, exercise self-

control, and achieve his potential. Any game should be built around well acknowledged educational concepts and strategies. The themes of educational games should be related to those disciplines. The learner works freely during the game-playing process because they are more engaged than they would be in a typical class. It should be mentioned that the game is primarily a teaching tool. Students engage in game lessons with enthusiasm, compete to win, and the teacher also teaches the student via them. The student is interested in playing games and thinks he can talk, listen, comprehend, and write in English. We are aware that the student should be the subject in the present educational process. The efficacy of teaching will rise if we place greater emphasis on interactive techniques. The ability to think independently is one of the most crucial skills that students of English must learn. Based on the expertise of pedagogues in the United States of America and England, English language instructors nowadays employ the following cutting-edge techniques:

- "Creative Problem Solving," in which the beginning of the story is read to the students and how it ends is left to their judgment;
- "Merry Riddles," in which students solve riddles to learn new vocabulary;
- "Quick answers," which increases the lesson's effectiveness;
- Warm-up exercises" using different games in the classroom to get students interested in the lesson;
- "Pantomime" method can be used in a lesson where very difficult concepts need to be explained or when written exercises have been completed and students are tired;
- "A chain story" method helps students develop oral speech;
- "Acting characters" method can be used in all types of lessons. People who work as interpreters, translators, writers, and poets might engage in class and interact with the students to teach the profession;
- "Thinkers meeting" poets and writers such as U. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be "invited". At such a time, using the wise words they said in the lesson will help young people to be educated as perfect people;
- The method "When pictures speak" is very convenient and helps to teach English and develop the oral speech of students, for this it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic;
- "Quiz cards" are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time.

As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own advantages. In all such methods, cooperation between the teacher and the student, and the active movement of the student in the educational process are envisaged.

CONCLUSION

In brief, adopting cutting-edge teaching techniques in English language lessons helps students' logical thinking abilities grow, their speech becomes fluent, and they learn to respond quickly and accurately. Such teaching techniques stimulate students' curiosity. The learner makes an effort to get well-prepared for the lessons. Students become engaged participants in their education as a result. In the future, when the educational system sets out to educate a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, we future instructors will contribute by more effectively figuring out how to employ cutting-edge technologies.

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